

INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA TANQIDIY O'QISH
STRATEGIYALARINING ROLI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til o'rganuvchilarga matnlarni qanday o'qish va ularni tanqidiy tahlil qilishda yordam beradigan bir qator o'qish strategiyalari muhokama qilinadi va umumlashtiriladi va o'qishni tushunishni yaxshilash uchun foydali strategiyalar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish strategiyalari, o'qishni tushunish, matn tuzilishi, jurnalni yuritish, eslatma.

**РОЛЬ СТРАТЕГИЙ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО ЧТЕНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ
АНГЛИЙСКИЙ**

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждается и обобщается ряд стратегий чтения, которые помогают изучающим языки читать тексты и критически анализировать их, а также предлагаются некоторые полезные стратегии для улучшения понимания прочитанного.

Ключевые слова: стратегии чтения, понимание прочитанного, структура текста, ведение журнала, конспектирование.

**THE ROLE OF CRITICAL READING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING
ENGLISH**

Abstract: This articles discusses and summaries a number of reading strategies that helps language learners how read texts and analyze them critically, and suggests some useful strategies to improve reading comprehension.

Key words: reading strategies, reading comprehension, text structure, keeping journal, note-taking.

It is very important for second language learners to know how to use critical reading strategies when they engage with text, because at present time there is a plethora of information on internet and social media platforms. The information on these sites can be trustable or untruthworthy, that is why readers need to have good critical reading strategies to approach with text with critical eye not only to construct meaning from texts, but also to be able to critically analyze the information presented to them. "Reading strategies can be defined as the cognitive processes involved when readers purposefully attempt to understand a text" (Barnett, 1989, p. 66). In

order to develop critical reading strategies on L2 learners teachers need to identify the key strategies which can be very handy tools for them to foster critical reading skills and they introduce these strategies to readers and practice them in the classroom so that they can effectively make use of them in real texts. Belenky and Nokes-Malach (2012) believe that teachers need to encourage interpretive knowledge whereby students can autonomously apply strategies to new texts, rather than simply replicating what they learned during guided practice sessions. Most experts state that through critical reading strategies teachers can evaluate whether the students can understand the texts they read or not. By constantly training to use critical reading strategies will make the students more understandable about the texts they read. If readers can make use of good reading strategies, they can communicate with texts directly without any obstacles and challenges and by adopting critical reading strategies, learners can navigate authentic texts to identify the author's purpose, persuasive elements, and bias to read and respond with an informed perspective. As Malcolm Larking says “By identifying the critical reading strategies students do not adequately use, and explicitly teaching such strategies, students will be able to read and evaluate authentic sources independently and with confidence”(2002,p,52). In this article, based on the survey results, this paper identifies a number of critical reading strategies that need greater attention in the classroom, and describes best practice for teaching them.

What is critical reading?

Learning how to read critically involves becoming actively engaged in what you read by first developing a clear understanding of the authors' ideas, then questioning and evaluating the arguments and evidence provided to those arguments. “Critical reading is an investigation into, and critique of the validity of arguments expressed in reading passages” (Malcolm Larking cited from Walz, 2017). Critical reading means that a reader applies certain process, models, questions, and theories that result in enhanced clarity and comprehension. The term critical reading has different meaning, but it can be widely divided into two separate traditions:

- 1) reading for academic success;
- 2) reading for social engagement..

According to Ryland and Ruthburn, Manarin, and Carey (2015, p, 4) reading critically for academic success includes following key skills:

1. Identifying patterns of textual elements;
2. distinguishing between main and subordinate ideas;
3. Evaluating credibility;
4. Making judgment about how a text argued;
5. Making relevant inference about the text.

Reading critically for social engagement intends to understand how a text can be utilized to attain social purposes, for instance, addressing gender and income disparity. To learn and understand critical reading, readers need to be aware of how literacy is utilized for social purposes, how an author might write to achieve their personal ends, and how one should treat their own reflection on a text's meaning with a sense of social purpose. "The tradition of critical reading for social purposes adheres to critical theory's questioning of, "inequalities and injustices that persist in society and how literacy instruction may become a site for contesting the status quo" (Siegel & Fernandez, 2000, p. 140).

Apart from these, there are a number of suggested steps that facilitate second language learners to be a critical reader.

1. Get ready to become a member of the writer's audience.

This means that before reading texts second language learners should learn about authors, the history of the author and the text, and also the author's anticipated audience.

2. Get ready to read an open mind.

Every reader seek knowledge, they do not copy a work to suit their own personalities. Their task as enlightened critical reader is to read what is on the page, giving the writer a fair chance to develop ideas and allowing yourself to reflect thoughtfully and objectively on the text.

3. Consider the title.

This may seem clear, but the title may provide clues to writer's attitude, goals, personal viewpoint or approach.

4. Read slowly.

Again, this approach obvious, but it is factor in "close reading". By slowing down, you will make more connections within the text.

5. Make notes.

While reading texts readers are advised to make marginal notes, underline and highlight important points, and note down the useful ideas to note-book, also they should do whatever works for themselves. Writing while reading facilitate readers' memory in many ways, especially by making a link that is unclear in the text concrete in their own writing.

6. Keep a reading journal.

In addition to note-taking, it is often helpful to regularly record your response and thought in a more permanent place that is your to consult. By developing a habit of reading and writing, both skills will improve.

Critical reading strategies.

Critical reading strategies are strategies that facilitate readers to comprehend and approach critically the text they read. Critical reading are the strategies utilised for activating students' critical thinking; at the same time they help readers to assess some information needed in reading text. Many critical reading strategies which can be utilized by the reader have been recommended by the experts. Accordind to Jurnal Buana Pendidikan cited from Hudson (2010, p, 102) states that critical reading requires the students to be able to analyze, synthesize, and evaluate what have been read. Many of the studies that examined thinking of proficient readers suggested seven or eight effective critical reading strategies utilized constantly by proficient readers. These strategies can be introduced by second language teachers in implementing critical reading. They are monitoring comprehension, understanding text structure, predicting, generating questions, answering questions, using mental image (visualizing), and summarizing.

1. Monitoring comprehension.

Monitoring comprehension means that readers identify how well they understand the text and what to do when their comprehension breaks down. Frequently, readers are baffled when or where they do not understand. They just continue reading. Here they must know that reading always make sense. When their comprehension breaks down, it is vital to address appropriate fix-up strategy. Readers need to identify whether a word has been incorrectly decoded or whether a word or sentence has been misunderstood in the given context. They also need to review whether they understand how the text is organized. Losing interest or concentration during the reading has negative impact on comprehension. These key elements help readers to monitor the text successfully.

2. Understanding the text structure.

To become successful and effective reader students need to deal with wide variety of text, because different texts are organized different way that readers have to know that the story will have a beginning, a middle and an ending. Every text have at least one problem and solution and consists of one or more characters. The students should know about setting, plot, and main idea.

3. Using Prior Knowledge/Predicting.

Predicting occurs before, during, after the reading. Readers address the knowledge from their own knowledge base to comprehend what they are reading. This personal knowledge base contains personal knowledge, knowledge of reading, and general knowledge about the world. Readers can understand better new ideas and data presented in the text. As we know everybody has diverse experiences in their life and they bring their own ideas to the text being read. This diversity make their understanding of the different that is why each readers personalizes the text.

4. *Generating questions.*

While students read the text, generating or asking question can be a very effective tool for them to clarify their thinking and understand better the text that they are reading. It is often observed that effective readers ask themselves question to clarify the meaning, make speculation about the text, identify writing style of the author of the text which helps them to make sense the text well.

5. *Answering questions.*

During the reading process responding questions from teacher, other students in the class or their peers can also be very beneficial for students to be a critical reader, because thinking about answers or listening to other students' explanations facilitate readers to make full comprehension of the text. Here it is very vital for teachers not only to ask quires from students but also teach them how to find the answers.

6. *Using mental image (visualizing).*

Visualizing refers to the capacity of readers' mind that helps to imagine what the authors are suggesting via their words on the page. Through the visualization and mental images, readers can relate what they are reading to something concrete a visual image, a feeling, a sound, a smell, or a taste.

7. *Making summary.*

Summarizing strategy is imperative to develop student comprehension and oral language proficiency. When students summarize the text, they can analyze what is crucial from they have read, relate what they have read to their personal experiences. Summarizing strategy facilitate students to improve their grasp of the main idea which is considered an important skill in comprehension. All of the critical reading strategies mentioned above are considered the best ones among others, if students tries to implement these skills, they can achieve their goal in reading without any doubt, because researchers discovered that these strategies are often utilized by proficient readers.

As we can see above, reading in a second or foreign language is such a challenging process that second language learners encounter various kind of obstacles until they become proficient readers. To reach proficient stage students enrich their minds not only with specific knowledge but also general knowledge about world that we live, because this knowledge to help them to develop reading comprehension. Moreover, skills and different reading strategies suggested and explained thoroughly can give students good assistance to be a prificient reader.

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